

A Study of the Composition of Jute Fibre with Special Reference to the Use of Chlorine Dioxide as an Analytical Reagent.

BY JOGENDRA KUMAR CHOWDHURY AND PHANINDRA CHANDRA MAJUMDAR.

Since the epoch-making investigations of Cross and Bevan on jute, little attention has been paid to the systematic study of the chemistry of the fibre which, according to these renowned investigators, constitutes an ideal material for the study of lignocelluloses. The methods of investigation in this field have, in recent years, undergone profound modification in many respects and it is highly desirable to apply these methods to the investigation of jute whose economic importance to this province is well known.

In this work, it is proposed to study the action of chlorine dioxide on jute with a view to determine the composition of the fibre and to compare the results with those obtained by the usual standard methods.

Hugo Muller ("Pflanzenfaser," p. 59; also Cross and Bevan, "Cellulose," 1918, p. 110) gives the following results of the analysis of jute, the figure for raw cellulose being obtained by treatment with bromine water and is hence very low while the figure for incrusting matter is proportionally high.

		Jute almost colourless.	Jute light yellow.
Moisture	...	9.93 %	9.64 %
Ash	...	0.68 ,,	...
Water extract	...	1.03 ,,	1.63 ,,
Fat and wax	...	0.39 ,,	0.32 ,,
Cellulose (raw)	...	64.24 ,,	63.05 ,,
Incrusting matter	...	23.73 ,,	25.36 ,,
	(by difference)		

The most recent analysis of jute is given as follows by Lehne and Scheppmann (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1925, 38, 93).

Moisture	...	11.42 %	
Ash	...	0.73 ,,	(calculated on dry jute).
Water extract	...	3.84 ,,	" " "
Fat and resin	...	1.03 ,,	" " "
Cellulose (raw)	...	78.84 ,,	" " "
Lignone	...	20.98 ,,	" " "
Pentosan (furfural)	...	10.25 ,,	" " "

The above figure for raw cellulose has been obtained by the chlorination method while lignone has been estimated by the method of Willstätter and Zechmeister.

Schmidt and Graumann (*Ber.*, 1921, **54**, 1860) observed that a solution of chlorine dioxide in water removes lignone without having any injurious effect on the polysaccharides. In the following experiments, the action of chlorine dioxide on jute has been studied and it has been found that both raw cellulose and lignone in jute may be estimated in one and the same operation, when the method of Schmidt and Graumann is modified by avoiding treatment with sodium sulphite. In that case, the figures for lignone agree substantially with those obtained by the standard method of Willstätter and Zechmeister while the figures for raw cellulose are higher than those obtained by the chlorination method. This is not due to any residual lignone in the cellulose but to the fact that the accompanying carbohydrates are very little affected by chlorine dioxide while they are partly destroyed by the chlorination method of Cross and Bevan. This discrepancy in the cellulose content, as determined by these methods, is not however of any material importance. Chlorination has been accepted as a standard method not because it gives a quantitative yield of pure cellulose but that it gives a higher yield of lignone-free raw cellulose than any other method. Not only a part of the hemicellulose is destroyed by the action of chlorine but cellulose itself is susceptible to this reagent. For this reason it will be seen that a higher percentage of α -cellulose is obtainable from jute treated with chlorine dioxide than from Cross and Bevan's jute cellulose.

Analysis of jute fibre.

About one foot from the lowest part of jute and some 2-3 feet from the upper part were rejected. The fibres, freed from woody matter, were cut to small pieces and freed from dust, dirt and adherent tissues by washing with soap. The fibres were then dried and stocked for the purpose of analysis.

Moisture.—Moisture was estimated by drying the fibre at 105° in vacuum over phosphorous pentoxide. The amount of moisture in the fibre was found to vary considerably with atmospheric humidity at different times of the year.

Wt. of air-dry jute (gm.)	Wt. of dried jute. (gm.)	% of moisture.	Remark.
1'6746	1'4986	10'51	Estimated in winter.
1'2576	1'1246	10'57	"
2'0	1'7162	14'19	Estimated in rainy season.

Ash.—Ash was estimated by igniting the jute in a platinum crucible.

Wt. of dry jute. (gm.)	Wt. of ash. (gm.)	% of ash on dry jute.
1.5786	0.0081	0.51
0.8618	0.0044	0.51

Fat and resin.—Fat and resin were estimated by repeated extraction with a mixture of alcohol and benzol (1 : 1).

Wt. of dry jute. (gm.)	Wt. of fat and resin (gm.)	% of fat and resin on dry jute.
6.7368	0.0568	0.848
3.6382	0.0308	0.846

Pentosans.—The pentosans were determined by treating the jute with hydrochloric acid (*d* 1.06) and estimating the furfural as phloroglucide according to the method of Tollens and Bödener (*Z. für Landwirt.*, 1910, 58, 232).

Wt. of dry jute. (gm.)	Wt. of phloroglucide (gm.)	Wt. of furfural. (gm.)	% of furfural on dry jute.
1.7162	0.2806	0.1607	9.369
..	0.2748	0.1574	9.176
..	0.2792	0.1599	9.322

Raw cellulose.—Raw cellulose is generally estimated directly after the removal of incrusting matters. A large variety of reagents (Cross and Bevan. "Cellulose," 1918, pp. 94-98) are used for the removal of lignone matter from lignocelluloses but all of them act chemically on cellulose matters as well, converting them into oxy- or hydro-celluloses and hydrolysing into soluble sugars. It is therefore a matter of great difficulty to estimate the total amount of cellulose matters. The chlorination method of Cross and Bevan is generally accepted as the best. The following results have been obtained by the use of this method.

Wt. of dry jute. (gm.)	Wt. of raw cellulose (dry). (gm.)	% of raw cellulose on dry jute.
0.7206	0.5434	75.40
0.6880	0.5119	74.40
0.6195	0.4734	76.40
0.6079	0.4505	74.10
0.4812	0.3571	74.20

Chlorine dioxide as a reagent for the estimation of raw cellulose.

It has already been indicated that chlorine attacks cellulose matters besides lignone. The chlorination method of Cross and Bevan cannot therefore be expected to give quantitative yield of cellulose matters,

In the following experiments, the action of chlorine dioxide is studied from a quantitative point of view and it is found that a much higher yield of raw cellulose is thus obtained, the accompanying polysaccharides being practically unaffected by this reagent.

In preparation of chlorine dioxide solution and in determining its strength, the directions of Schmidt and Graumann have generally been followed (*Ber.*, 1923, 56, 23; 1921, 54, 1862).

Procedure.—A weighed quantity of jute fibre was immersed in chlorine dioxide solution of known strength, free from any trace of chlorine, in a hydrogen peroxide bottle which was then stoppered, shaken thoroughly and kept in the dark at room temperature. The bottle was shaken occasionally and a sample of jute taken out and examined for lignone from time to time. This was done qualitatively with the help of the microscope, while quantitatively lignone was estimated by the well-known method of Willstätter and Zechmeister. The lignone matter when acted on by chlorine dioxide became mostly soluble in water and the rest was easily loosened from the fibres which were then shaken with excess of water and washed thoroughly until the washings were perfectly clear and free from any trace of chlorine. The fibre was then pressed on a Buchner funnel and dried in the sun. The fibre thus obtained was almost white in colour, had good tensile strength, though it turned yellowish on prolonged exposure to air. In order to study the best conditions for delignification, the fibre was subjected to the action of chlorine dioxide of different strengths and for different periods of time. As in the case of chlorination, the best results were obtained by repeated treatment with chlorine dioxide solution, though in this case two treatments were found generally sufficient.

TABLE I.

Effect of time on delignification of jute fibre by means of a single treatment with chlorine dioxide solution.

Strength of the solution = 2.5 %. Volume of the solution = 350 c.c.

Wt. of dry jute. (gm.)	Time of treatment (hours).	Wt. of raw cellulose (dry). (gm.)	% of cellulose (on dry jute).	% of lignone in the cellulose thus obtd.
22.3575	24	19.8159	86.4	2.01
"	48	19.0285	85.17	0.79
"	72	19.0	85.0	0.63

TABLE II.

Effect of repeated treatments with chlorine dioxide solution of different strengths.

Period of each treatment is 24 hours.

Strength of ClO_2 solution %	Volume (c.c.)	No. of treatments.	Wt. of dry jute (gm.)	Wt. of raw cellulose (dry). (gm.)	% of raw cellulose.	% of lignone in raw cellulosa.
0.31	130	1	6.3657	5.7989	91.1	8.26
..	..	2	6.2523	5.5120	89.16	4.79
..	270	3	11.5756	9.9618	86.0	1.83
0.62	130	1	6.6981	5.9841	89.34	4.83
..	..	2	6.2121	5.3840	86.67	2.18
..	200	3	8.2243	6.8471	83.25	1.66
1.25	130	1	4.3125	4.1915	87.10	2.67
..	..	2	4.6953	4.0384	86.01	1.78
..	..	3	4.6414	3.9834	85.83	1.40
2.5	350	1	22.3575	19.8159	88.4	2.01
..	..	2	22.3575	19.0630	85.0	0.603
..	..	3	22.8055	19.3391	84.8	0.54

From the above tables it may be observed that delignification may be effected either by prolonged treatment or by repeated action of chlorine dioxide solution of 2.5% strength.

By comparing the above figures of cellulose content with those obtained by the chlorination method it will be noticed that the yield by chlorine dioxide method is about 10% higher. The high α -cellulose and furfural contents in the cellulose thus obtained indicate that the cellulose and hemicelluloses are very little affected by this reagent while the good tensile strength of the treated fibre indicates that the gummy matter is also intact. The fibre crumbles to ultimate cells when boiled with alkaline substances or with sodium sulphite. The initial white colour of the delignified fibre however slowly gives place to a light yellow colour, though when analysed by Willstätter and Zechmeister's method, only traces of lignone can be detected. As the loss in the weight of the treated fibre is equivalent to the lignone content of jute, it is reasonable to assume that practically all

the ingredients present in the original jute with the exception of lignone are also present in the delignified fibre which is therefore an eminently suitable material for the investigation of the composition of jute.

Besides keeping the cellulose matters intact, the chlorine peroxide treatment requires less time and attention and is very simple to carry out.

Lignone.—Of the various methods for the estimation of lignone only a few are of practical importance. These consist of the direct methods of (1) treatment with 42% hydrochloric acid, (2) treatment with 72% sulphuric acid at room temperature and (3) treatment with 1% hydrochloric acid under 6 atmospheres pressure and (4) the indirect method of estimating methoxyl according to the method of Zeisel. In all these methods, the cellulose has to be completely destroyed. The quantitative removal of lignone with the preservation of cellulose always removes a part of the cellulose matters and thus makes the estimation of lignone unreliable. The following figures for lignone content of jute have been obtained by Willstätter and Zechmeister's method as modified by Krall ("Schwalbe and Sieber-Betriebs-Kontrolle in der Zellstoff und Papier-Industrie," p. 102).

Wt. of dry jute (gm.).	Wt. of lignone (gm.).	% of lignone (on dry jute).	Mean percentage of lignone.
4.4715	0.7038	15.74	
„	0.6842	15.30	15.524
„	0.6952	15.532	

Chlorine dioxide as a reagent for the estimation of lignone.

The following figures for lignone content in jute have been obtained by treatment of jute with 2.5% chlorine dioxide solution, the procedure being the same as described in the case of cellulose estimation. It will be seen that the results are in fair agreement with those obtained by Willstätter's method, which, for the sake of comparison, is noted in the last column of the following table.

TABLE III.

Wt. of dry jute (gm.).	Wt. of treated jute (gm.).	Loss of weight (lignone) %.	Lignone by Willstätter's method.
22.3575	19.00	15.0	15.524 %
„	19.0039	15.0	„
22.8055	19.3391	15.2	„

It will be observed that this is the only method for the estimation of lignone which works without destruction of cellulose matter and that both cellulose and lignone may be estimated in one and the same operation. The removal of lignone is better and quicker when the fibre is freed from fat and resin by previous extraction with benzol-alcohol. As in the case of cellulose, treatment with sodium sulphite or even with boiling water has to be avoided.

Composition of cellulose fibre obtained from jute by chlorine dioxide treatment.

The cellulose obtained by chlorine dioxide treatment consists of α -cellulose, hemicellulose (pentosans and hexosans) including gummy matter and some pectin substances. Any nitrogenous matter present in jute, would also be present in the fibre as proteins are not attacked by chlorine dioxide (Euler, *Cellulosechem.*, 4, 109).

The following table gives the characteristic colour tests of the fibre obtained by chlorine dioxide treatment, when observed under the microscope. It gives all the standard colour reactions of cellulose.

TABLE IV.

Reagent.	Cotton.	Raw jute.	Chlorine dioxide treated fibre.
Iodine solution ...	No coloration	Greenish yellow.	No coloration.
Phloroglucinol-hydrochloric acid.	„	Bright reddish violet.	„
Zinc chloride—iodine solution.	Violet ...	Greenish yellow.	Violet.

When the fibre was treated with Schweitzer's reagent, it swelled and ultimately dissolved to a viscous solution, but little change of jute under similar condition was observed.

Estimation of moisture in raw cellulose.

Wt. of raw cellulose (air dry) (gm.).	Wt. of moisture. (gm.)	% of moisture.	Remark.
1'1822	0'1041	8'8	Estimated in winter.
0'8591	0'0756	8'8	„
0'8352	0'1053	12'64	Estimated in the rainy season.

Estimation of ash in raw cellulose.

Wt. of raw cellulose (dry) (gm.).	Wt. of ash. (gm.)	% of ash on dry raw cellulose.
0·5782	0·0019	0·328
0·7994	0·0026	0·327

Estimation of α -cellulose in raw cellulose.—The α -cellulose was determined by treatment with cold caustic soda solution of 17·5% (Jentgen, *Kunststoffe*, 1911, 1, 165). A weighed quantity of the cellulose fibre was rubbed in a mortar with 17·5% caustic soda solution, allowed to stand for half an hour and diluted with water. The whole mass was then sucked through a linen filter in a Buchner funnel. The residue was washed thoroughly with water until completely free from alkali. Finally it was washed with hot dilute acetic acid and again with water, dried and weighed.

This method of estimating α -cellulose is not above criticism, as the alkali of such strength may convert the cellulose into alkali-soluble oxycellulose and into the highly voluminous cellulose hydrate. But as the other methods of removing hemicelluloses by hydrolysis with weak acids, either alone or in presence of glycerine, attack the α -cellulose strongly, this alkali treatment remains the best method for the estimation of α -cellulose.

TABLE V.

Lignone content of the raw cellulose is 0·54%.

Wt. of dry raw cellulose. (gm.)	Wt. of dry α -cellulose. (gm.)	% of α -cellulose on raw cellulose.	% of α -cellulose on dry jute.
0·6521	0·3950	71·545	60·677
0·6715	0·4085	71·478	60·608

It may be pointed out that this method gives a higher yield of α -cellulose than the chlorination method, and is therefore to be preferred in the quantitative estimation of α -cellulose. In the chlorination method, the halogen evidently attacks not only the hemicellulose to a more or less extent, but the α -cellulose also, as will be seen from the following table.

TABLE VI.

Determination of α -cellulose from the raw cellulose obtained by chlorination method.

Wt. of dry raw cellulose. (gm.)	Wt. of dry α -cellulose. (gm.)	% of α -cellulose on raw cellulose.	% of α -cellulose on dry jute.
0.5434	0.4154	76.44	57.646
0.4505	0.3515	78.02	57.82

In order to test the purity of α -cellulose from raw cellulose, obtained by chlorine dioxide treatment, its ash and furfural contents have been determined and are given in the following tables.

TABLE VII.

Ash in α -cellulose.

Wt. of α -cellulose. (gm.)	Wt. of ash. (gm.)	% of ash on α -cellulose.
0.9893	0.0014	0.141
0.8421	0.0012	0.142

TABLE VIII.

Furfural in α -cellulose.

Wt. of α -cellulose. (gm.)	Wt. of phloroglucide. (gm.)	Wt. of furfural. (gm.)	% of furfural on α -cellulose.
1.8113	0.0334	0.0196	1.082
2.0747	0.0384	0.0225	1.084

The α -cellulose obtained by chlorine dioxide method is evidently purer than that obtained by Lehne and Schepmann from jute by chlorination method, which gave 2.4% furfuroids (*loc. cit.*).

Hemicellulose in raw cellulose.

It has already been shown that hemicellulose is not removed by the chlorine dioxide treatment so long as the treatment with sodium sulphite is avoided. The hemicellulose can therefore be easily estimated by taking the difference between total cellulose

and α -cellulose. It is to be noted that the quantitative methods for the determination of hemicellulose are at present far from being satisfactory. This is due to the fact that the hemicellulose is attacked and removed along with lignone by all other methods of delignification. This method will, therefore, be of great service in the estimation of hemicelluloses as well as for the investigation of their constitution and chemical properties. The result obtained is, however, slightly higher than the actual amount of hemicellulose, owing to the presence of small amount of lignone (0.54%) and any protein or pectin matter that might be present in the raw cellulose.

TABLE IX.

Wt. of raw cellulose dry (gm.).	Wt. of α -cellulose. (gm.)	Wt. of hemicellulose. (gm.)	% of hemicellulose on raw cellulose.	% of hemicellulose on dry jute.
0.5521	0.3950	0.1571	28.45	24.13
0.5715	0.4085	0.1630	28.52	24.18

Pentosans in raw cellulose.

That the pentosan content of jute fibre has not been materially attacked or removed by treatment with chlorine dioxide is shown by the estimation of the furfural content of the original jute as well as of the raw cellulose. The estimations were carried out as before.

TABLE X.

Wt. of raw cellulose (gm.)	Wt. of phloroglucide (gm.)	Wt. of furfural (gm.)	% of furfural on raw cellulose.
1.7120	0.3000	0.1718	10.04
1.7974	0.3160	0.1776	9.88
1.7260	0.2996	0.1716	9.94

It will be seen that very little of the pentosan matter has been removed; thus taking the furfural content of jute (lignone, 15.524%) as 9.2%, the calculated furfural content of the delignified fibre is approximately 10.8% whereas about 10% furfural was actually found above. In the chlorination method, however, the pentosans are considerably removed, as is shown by their furfural content. Thus Cross and Bevan state that their raw jute cellulose gave only 4.8%

furfuroids. Lehne and Scheppmann obtained about 10·5% furfuroids in jute (lignone content being 20·98%), and 8·3% in the raw cellulose obtained by chlorination method. If the pentosans were quite unaffected by chlorination, the furfuroids in the delignified jute would amount to 13·3%, while actually they found 8·3%. Evidently a considerable amount of pentosans was removed by the chlorination method followed by them.

Estimation of gummy matter in raw cellulose.

Gummy matter is generally estimated in raw cellulose, isolated from lignocellulose and not in the crude fibre itself. The general method used is that of Kast ("Untersuchung der Spring- und Zundstoffe," 1909, p. 919) which consists in treating cellulose with 5% caustic soda solution. An alkali of this strength would dissolve part of the lignone matter, in addition to the gummy substance, which being protected by lignone would only be incompletely extracted, and would thus vitiate the result. In the isolation of the cellulose matter by usual methods, however, wood gum is largely affected and removed. This is particularly the case when the fibre is washed with alkaline materials or sodium sulphite solution. For these reasons the cellulose obtained from lignocelluloses by the ordinary methods is obtained in the form of ultimate cells. This cellulose material cannot, therefore, be expected to give a quantitative yield of the gummy matter. By the chlorine dioxide treatment, however, the delignified fibre retains its original tensile strength, and evidently the gummy substance, and is reduced to ultimate cells only when boiled with dilute sodium sulphite solution, soda and other alkaline substances. This substance is, therefore, eminently suitable for the quantitative determination of the gummy substance, as well as for the investigation of its chemical nature.

Procedure.—A weighed quantity of the raw cellulose fibre (about 15 gms.) was taken in a conical flask and covered with 300 c.c. of exactly 5% caustic soda solution. The whole was then allowed to stand for 24 hours with frequent shaking. The liquid was filtered and the residue washed with water, the washings being added to the filtrate, which was made up to a definite volume (400 c.c.). To a small amount of the filtrate (100 c.c.) about thrice the volume of rectified spirit was added and the liquid shaken vigorously. It was then neutralised with *N*-hydrochloric acid using phenolphthalein as

the indicator. The acid was then added in slight excess, and the precipitate was allowed to settle for 24 hours, collected on a dried and weighed filter, washed with rectified spirit and ether and was finally dried. To purify the gummy matter thus obtained, it was powdered and dissolved in dilute alkali. The solution was neutralised with *N*-hydrochloric acid, and the gummy substance reprecipitated by rectified spirit, washed as before, and dried. The gummy matter, thus obtained, was a white amorphous substance.

Wt. of dry cellulose (raw) in gm.	Vol. of filtrate in c.c.	Wt. of gum (gm.)	Total wt. of gum (gm.)	% of gum on raw cellulose.	% of gum on jute.
14.9302	100	0.5048			
	"	0.5052	2.023	13.56	11.49
	"	0.4970			
	"	0.5160			

The gummy matter, isolated in the above manner, is not a homogeneous substance, but is mainly composed of pentosans (and hexosans), mixed perhaps with a small amount of pectin matter. This is indicated by the estimations of furfuroids as well as methoxyl.

TABLE XI.

Furfural in the gummy matter.

Wt. of gum. (gm.)	Wt. of phloroglucide. (gm.)	Wt. of furfural. (gm.)	% of furfural on gum.
1.9076	0.949	0.5425	41.48
0.8450	0.600	0.3431	40.61

Methoxyl in the gummy matter.

Methoxyl was estimated by treating the gum with hydriodic acid according to the well-known Zeisel's method.

TABLE XII.

Wt. of gum. (gm.)	Wt. of silver-iodide. (gm.)	% of methoxyl.
0.366	0.0746	2.688
0.333	0.068	2.693

It is important to study the physical and chemical properties of this gummy substance thoroughly, as the tensile strength and other

physical properties of jute, which determine the industrial importance of the fibre, depend very largely on this gummy matter.

Attempts were made to make the delignified fibre less susceptible to the action of alkali, but without success. It is only when a small percentage of lignone matter is present, and thus protects the gummy substance that the fibre can stand a certain extent of washing with slightly alkaline matter. It has been observed that when a minimum amount of 4.79% lignone matter is present in the fibre it is not very susceptible to washing. Whether a fibre with this lignone content is suitable enough for textile purposes, can be determined only by actual spinning tests. The completely delignified fibre, obtained by washing with chlorine dioxide, is of practically white colour, and may, perhaps, be used as a substitute for cotton where little or no washing is necessary.

Summary.

1. It has been found that the highest percentage of raw cellulose is obtained from jute by washing with 2.5% aqueous chlorine dioxide solution without subsequent washing with sodium sulphite.

2. Estimation of lignone and cellulose matters may be made simultaneously in the above operation, and thus save time and expense. The figures for lignone, obtained by this method, agree substantially with those obtained by Willstätter's method.

3. A method has been developed for the quantitative estimation of hemicellulose, and of the gummy substance in jute, as they are not affected in any appreciable degree by the above treatment. For this reason, this is a very suitable material for the isolation and investigation of the chemical nature of these substances.

4. The chlorine dioxide treatment gives higher yield of α -cellulose than the chlorination method, and is therefore to be preferred for this purpose to the chlorination method.

5. The ash and furfural contents of α -cellulose, isolated in the above process, are extremely small, and thus testify to the purity of the α -cellulose.

6. Delignified jute with some 4-5% lignone has been found less susceptible to washing than the completely delignified fibre.

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CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
DACCA UNIVERSITY.

